

FATIGUE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES UNDER COMPLEX CYCLIC LOADING

J. Andersons, M. Miķelsons, V. Tamužs
Institute of Polymer Mechanics, Rīga, Latvia

V.A. Limonov
CNIISM, Hotkovo, Russia

ABSTRACT

With the area of application of laminated composites steadily widening, spectrum of loading modes composite members have to be designed to resist diversifies. Service loading often causes a complex stress state with nonproportional cyclic stress tensor components. Two basic complex loading modes - biaxial out-of-phase loading and biaxial loading with different stress ratios - have been investigated experimentally and analytical durability prediction methods elaborated. Tests concerning phase lag effect were carried out on tubular filament-wound samples of Kevlar/epoxy type composite. Durability was found to decrease with increasing phase shift between axial and torsional load components. Besides, tubular glass fabric/epoxy composite specimens were used to study the effect of stress ratio mismatch. Ply discount method was modified to account for complex stress path. Calculated S-N curves agree reasonably well with experimental data.

Keywords: fatigue durability, complex loading, laminate, Kevlar/epoxy, glass/epoxy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Increasingly widespread use of composite materials in structural members subjected to fatigue loading raises the importance of reliable design and service life prediction methods. Service loading, as a rule, is complex in that it is multiaxial and different components of it are generally not proportional. Little effort has been made in studying the effect of loading with complex stress path, as most of fatigue research is confined to proportional cyclic loading mode, e.g. [1]. It should be mentioned that by varying phase lag of load components only, remarkable variation of damage accumulation rate in composite was observed [2].

Durability prediction for isotropic materials implicitly involves two stages. First, a critical plane is to be determined along which fatigue crack will propagate. Then fatigue failure criterion or crack propagation law is formulated in terms of stresses acting on that plane and solved for time to failure. Inherent heterogeneity of composites in various structural levels leading to weak directions and planes in the material facilitates solution of the first problem mentioned above - fracture paths

are largely predetermined by design of material and insensitive to loading path. It makes fatigue life prediction under complex loading for composite materials even more tractable than for isotropic ones. Below, study of fatigue under two regular complex loading modes, namely combination of static shear and cyclic compression and biaxial out-of-phase loading is presented.

2. FATIGUE FAILURE MODEL FOR LAMINATED COMPOSITE

Regular structure of continuous fiber reinforced laminates with much of pre-failure damage accumulation localized within the plies has led to elaboration of ply discount method for static and fatigue strength prediction under plane stress state. Ply discount method in fatigue implies utilizing of uniaxial ply durability data, ply failure criterion under complex loading encountered within the laminate, a mechanism of reduction of elasticity constants of a ply after its failure, and damage accumulation model on the ply level. Detailed description of the implementation of this procedure for proportional cycling is given in [1].

To account for complex loading path, ply failure criterion is to be modified. The geometrical approach of phenomenological failure theories offers a straightforward way of doing it. It has been shown that critical stress state under static or proportional cyclic loading can be represented by a surface $F(\sigma_{ij}, \Sigma) = 1$ in the stress space, where Σ denotes a set of experimentally determined strengths under simple loading modes. Assuming that regardless of loading path failure takes place when stress trajectory touches the failure surface $F(\sigma_{ij}, \Sigma(N))$ and knowing analytical expression for the latter, fatigue failure criterion for complex loading path given can be derived. Concrete examples for Hashin's criterion and two complex loading modes are given below.

3. EFFECT OF STRESS RATIO MISMATCH

3.1. Material and loading mode

Tests were performed on tubular samples produced by tangential winding of epoxy resin preimpregnated glass fabric on a steel mandrel. The reinforcement was satin fabric with linear density of 24 fibers/cm in the warp and 32 fibers/cm in the weft direction. Weft direction coincided with the direction of the axis of the specimen. Wall thickness amounted to 2.5 ± 0.3 mm (10 layers of fabric), fiber volume fraction 45%.

Complex fatigue loading was carried out on Instron-1343 setup. Different levels of static torque ($R=1$) were applied combined with axial cyclic compression. Frequency of the latter was $f=6$ Hz, stress ratio $R=50$. Ratios of static shear stress to strength studied included $\sigma_{12}/\Sigma_{12}=0.33, 0.55, 0.77$. Corresponding stress trajectory in the space of applied stresses is shown schematically in Fig. 1 together with fatigue strength surface.

3.2. Test results and prediction

Experimental static failure surface for combined axial and torsional loading of glass fabric composite [3] can be readily approximated by the quadratic Hashin's failure criterion [4]. Utilizing the approach described above, we arrive at the following relation for the critical cyclic stress:

$$\sigma_{22}(N) = \Sigma_{22}(N) (1 - (\sigma_{12}/\sigma_{12}(t))^2)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where $\Sigma_{22}(N)$ - fatigue strength under compression, $\sigma_{12}(t)$ - long-term shear strength at $t=N/f$, where f is cyclic loading frequency. For relatively short test duration $\sigma_{12}(t)$ may be substituted by

Figure 1. Stress trajectory (1) and fatigue failure surface (2) for combined cyclic compression and static shear.

a short-term static strength Σ_{12} . S-N curves calculated according to (1) and this assumption are shown in Fig. 2 by solid lines together with experimental data. Appreciable deviation of the theoretical prediction is observed only for the highest static torque level $\sigma_{12}/\Sigma_{12}=0.77$. It is caused by using static shear strength in calculations when applied shear stress becomes close to long-term strength [3].

As no experimental long-term strength data were available, curve-fitting was employed to evaluate the time dependence of static shear strength from one fatigue diagram under complex loading. The functional form of dependence was assumed to be the same as for cyclic fatigue, ie $\sigma_{12}(N)/\Sigma_{12}=A-B\lg N$. Best fit of line (1) for $\sigma_{12}/\Sigma_{12}=0.77$ was obtained at $A=1.19$ and $B=0.067$. S-N diagrams calculated using these parameters are shown in Fig. 2 by dashed lines.

Figure 2. Fatigue data at $\sigma_{12}/\Sigma_{12}=0.33$ (■), 0.55 (▲), 0.77 (□) and predictions accounting for (---) and neglecting (—) reduction of shear strength.

4. EFFECT OF PHASE LAG

4.1. Material and loading mode

Tubular thin-wall specimens of aramid fiber/epoxy matrix composite with lay-up $[\pm 30^\circ; 90^\circ; \pm 30^\circ]$ were tested. Geometrical characteristics and technology of manufacturing of the specimens are described in [5]. Due to variation in yarn stretching force fiber volume fraction depended on reinforcement angle. For helically wound plies (reinforcement direction with respect to specimen axis $\phi = 30^\circ$) it was 60...65%, hoop plies ($\phi = 90^\circ$) - 65...70%.

Biaxial fatigue tests of combined tension and torsion were performed on universal test machine Instron-1343 under load control. Loading frequency was 17 Hz, stress ratio 0.1. Phase lag values ψ studied comprised 0° , 90° and 180° . Corresponding stress trajectories in the space of applied stresses are presented in Fig.3.

Figure 3. Stress trajectories for complex cyclic tension and shear with phase lags $\psi = 0^\circ$ (1), 90° (2), 180° (3).

4.2. Test results and prediction

It has been shown in [5] that Hashin's criterion is valid for both static and cyclic proportional loading of unidirectionally reinforced specimens of the aramid/epoxy composite investigated. Modifying the criterion for out-of-phase loading, we come to the following expression for onset of matrix cracking:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22m} + \sigma_{22a} \sin \omega t}{\Sigma_{22}(N)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12m} + \sigma_{12a} \sin(\omega t + \psi)}{\Sigma_{12}(N)} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

where Σ_{22} , Σ_{12} are fatigue strengths under loading with stress ratios $(\sigma_{22m}-\sigma_{22a})/(\sigma_{22m}+\sigma_{22a})$ and $(\sigma_{12m}-\sigma_{12a})/(\sigma_{12m}+\sigma_{12a})$ correspondingly. The criterion of fiber fracture does not change its form. Due to the lack of experimental information concerning out-of-phase fatigue of unidirectional composite, validity of criterion (2) can be determined only indirectly, by comparing predicted fatigue diagrams of laminated composite with test results.

Apart from introducing phase shifts between stress tensor components acting in the plies, out-of-phase loading causes variation of stress ratios as well. To account for the effect of it, Goodman diagrams of a ply obtained in [6] were used. Experimentally determined and predicted fatigue diagrams are shown in Fig. 4. Specimens failed in shear instability mode. Exhaustion of load bearing capacity was preceded by localized splitting of helically wound layers and limited fiber bundle pull-out.

Introduction of phase lag leads to an appreciable reduction of fatigue strength that can be predicted by the proposed modified ply-by-ply failure analysis.

Figure 4. Fatigue data and predicted S-N diagrams for out-of-phase loading with phase lag $\psi=0^\circ(\square)$, $90^\circ(\blacktriangle)$, $180^\circ(\blacksquare)$.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It has been observed that varying stress trajectory alone can significantly alter fatigue strength of laminated composite. Therefore service loading path should be closely followed in laboratory tests to obtain reliable fatigue data. Ply discount method provides engineering tools for assessing durability under complex loading by utilizing fatigue diagrams of constituting laminae.

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FRACTURE

